

Time to care – care for time - How spending more time for care than consumption helps to mitigate climate change

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2 **Barbara Smetschka^{1*}, Veronika Gaube¹, Katharina Mader²**

3 ¹ Institute of Social Ecology (SEC) University of Natural Resources & Life Sciences, Vienna
4 (BOKU), Vienna, Austria

5 ² Department of Economics, Vienna University of Economics and Business (WU), Vienna, Austria

6 *** Correspondence:**

7 Barbara Smetschka

8 barbara.smetschka@boku.ac.at

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24

25 **Abstract**

26 Mitigating climate change requires urgent reductions of emissions. Demand-side measures focus on
27 footprints (direct and indirect emissions) of consumption. Analyzing time use brings a novel
28 perspective to discuss the carbon implications of everyday life and the potentials and limitations for
29 decarbonizing consumption. In this paper we show how time-use studies can serve as a bridging
30 concept between sustainability studies and the analysis of human well-being for all.

31 We introduce a functional time-use perspective differentiating personal, committed, contracted and
32 free time. We calculate average carbon intensity of everyday activities in Austria 2010 combining
33 Austrian Time-use Survey and Austrian Household Budget Survey with Eora-MRIO. We find that
34 these activities differ widely in carbon intensity. Personal time is relatively low-carbon intense, while
35 free time activities show large variation in terms of CO₂e footprint/hour.

36 The traditional gendered division of labor shapes the time-use patterns of women and men, with
37 implications for their carbon footprints. Reassessing and sharing unpaid reproductive caring activities
38 is the basis for solving some urgent ecological and social problems. The way household members use
39 their time, the resource demand of households and infrastructure and services provided by
40 communities entail each other. Time use, time prosperity and especially time scarcity determine our
41 quality of life. Caring activities as “time to care” play a crucial role for pathways towards socio-
42 ecological transformation and gender equality.

43 Further research in the field of time, care and gender studies could be based on this framework and
44 add new perspectives on research on sustainable development.

45

46

47 **1 Introduction**

48 Mitigating climate change to achieve the goal of staying below 1.5°C of warming requires urgent
49 reductions of emissions. Demand-side measures mostly focus on the footprints of consumption,
50 considering direct and indirect emissions of CO₂e. Analyzing society-nature interactions and
51 pathways for a socio-ecological transformation is based on a perspective on everyday practices
52 within specific societies and their specific environmental consequences (Haberl et al., 2021; Plank et
53 al., 2021). Time-use studies provide data on everyday activities and their implications on well-being
54 (Gershuny, 2011), the environment (Adam, 1997), gender relations (Sullivan, 1997) or the
55 organization of work and care (Schor, 1997, 2010b) to name but a few authors and fields of research.
56 Ecological economics and climate sciences provide insights on the carbon footprints of these
57 activities (Minx and Baiocchi, 2010; Wiedenhofer et al., 2018).

58 In this perspective article we discuss how time-use studies can serve as a bridging concept between
59 sustainability studies and the analysis of human well-being especially when addressing caring
60 activities. This represents a novel and original approach, which is interdisciplinary as it combines
61 time-use research from social sciences with concepts of quality of life and just transition discussed in
62 humanities and political ecology with the aim to find a method to quantify CO₂e emissions of the
63 everyday practice of households in line with climate sciences.

64 Care has hitherto not been discussed a lot in its relation to sustainable consumption. This new
65 interdisciplinary pioneering research field can draw from different angles and approaches to start a
66 fruitful discussion on a topic which will gain a lot of importance in the near future. Therefore, here
67 we present both an assessment on recent works on the question of care, time-use and climate change
68 and a new perspective on time-use data analyzed for the case of Austria, trying to show how this can
69 contribute to the evolving topic of "Sustainable Consumption and Care". The last time-use survey for
70 Austria was conducted in 2010, providing the base for our analysis of the carbon footprint of
71 everyday activities (Smetschka 2019). We hereby lay the ground for further discussion and analysis
72 with newer data (i.e. next round of time-use surveys in Austria 2023 and international compilations).
73 The recent pandemic brought a disruption in time-use and the need for caring activities, thereby
74 giving even more importance to future analysis.

75 The relevant conceptual approaches of socio-ecological transformation and time-use studies and their
76 link to questions of sustainable development, care and gender equality is presented in chapter 2,
77 followed by discussing the results of research on CO₂ footprints per activities and the findings from a
78 recent literature assessment in chapter 3.

79 **2 Relevant concepts adding to a new perspective**

80 This paper proposes to address sustainable consumption and care from a time-use perspective based
81 on concepts of 2.1. socio-ecological transformation and 2.2. sustainable development and in context
82 of 2.3 research on gender relations. In 2.4 concepts of functional time-use and carbon footprints are
83 introduced referring to a case study analyzed for Austria 2010.

84 **2.1 Socio-ecological transformation**

85 Social Ecology – as a scientific approach (Haberl et al., 2016) developed at the Institute of Social
86 Ecology in Vienna – aims to describe the interaction between social and natural systems. Two
87 concepts, social metabolism and colonization of natural systems, constitute the core of socio-
88 ecological theory. Social Ecology is based on the concept of overlapping and interlinked natural and

89 cultural systems, showing a systems' dynamic in which social development is not independent of the
 90 natural environment and ecological and societal structures and processes are interlinked. Society
 91 understood as a hybrid based in both the natural and the cultural sphere, therefore, cannot be analysed
 92 as a whole exclusively from a natural or a social science perspective (Fischer-Kowalski and Weisz,
 93 1999). One core feature of societal interventions into natural systems is that they require human
 94 working time (Fischer-Kowalski and Haas, 2016) in the form of paid and unpaid work, which is the
 95 focus of interdisciplinary time-use studies.

97 2.2 Sustainable development and time

98 The long-time scale of environmental changes like climate change, biodiversity loss or soil
 99 degradation is in its very logic conflicting with short-term rewards and economic interests. Rhythms
 100 and synchronization of everyday life affect human well-being via the notion of time scarcity or
 101 prosperity. Conflicting demands on individuals who have to produce and reproduce all spheres of
 102 their lives add pressure. Resource use is linked to economic demand and grows irrespective of
 103 production or regeneration rates (Hartard et al., 2006; Biesecker and Hofmeister, 2010; Biesecker et
 104 al., 2012).

105 In scientific and political discourse often, the quest to dematerialize everyday life is linked to
 106 promoting a more frugal lifestyle. Here we argue that a socio-ecological time-use perspective can be
 107 more productive than promoting austerity to achieve reductions in resource use. Spending a good
 108 time with low carbon activities can lead to solutions for enhancing human quality of life and lower
 109 carbon emissions at the same time (Schor, 2010b; Reisch, 2015) providing both more care and
 110 climate justice.

111

112 Figure 1: Decoupling options, adapted from (Fischer-Kowalski and Steinberger, 2017)

113 Time-use is a concept used in sustainability discourses, mostly within research on degrowth and
 114 well-being. Fischer-Kowalski defines three types of decoupling shown in Figure 1: the critique of
 115 welfare, critique of efficiency and critique of consumerism, which all comprise a time component.

116 Time use is an important aspect of well-being and the critique of welfare initiates the question of how
 117 to measure well-being beyond monetary indicators and on how to provide necessary caring activities.
 118 The critique of consumerism links to questions of sustainable consumption: How much goods or
 119 services and how much time do we need for wellbeing? The third critique points to the question, if
 120 efficiency gains can make up for straining demands on ever-faster living and its impact on well-being
 121 on the one hand and for higher demands on resource use through additional efficient production on
 122 the other hand.

123 Speed is an as important factor of our economy as efficiency; typically, both translate into “no waste
 124 of time” rather than “no waste of material”. On the contrary, speed and efficiency tend to lead to the
 125 substitution of slow low-carbon activities and home production with high material and energy intense
 126 technologies, goods or practices. Here, general physics applies: the faster you move, the more energy
 127 you need. ‘Having no time for anything’ as the epigram of modern life leaves no time for concerns
 128 about climate change or other environmental or societal issues (Rosa and Trejo-Mathys, 2013).

129 When the goal is to achieve well-being for all in an ecologically and economically sustainable way,
 130 the question of an adequate understanding of well-being or quality of life (QOL) is central to
 131 sustainable development. In sustainability sciences, it is, therefore, important to find indicators to
 132 assess quality of life and changes therein adequately. Time-use is an integrative aspect of many facets
 133 of quality of life and is considered essential in its monitoring (Carlstein, 1981; Moe, 1998; Mischau
 134 and Oechsle, 2005; Mückenberger and Boulin, 2005; Schaffer, 2007; Fischer-Kowalski and
 135 Schaffartzik, 2008; Garhammer, 2008). The terms ‘time scarcity’ and ‘time affluence’
 136 (Rinderspacher, 2002; Heitkötter, 2006; Kränzle Nagel and Beham, 2007; Schor, 2010a) are used to
 137 link economic and social factors and to find alternatives to a solely economic notion of growth and
 138 development beyond a more sustainable consumption (Sanne, 2002; Graaf, 2003; Jackson, 2005;
 139 Kasser and Sheldon, 2010). Finally, the European Statistical Office (Eurostat) states that we need a
 140 measurement of QOL beyond GDP (Eurostat, 2018) and plans to include time-use data in future
 141 European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (SILC) surveys. Addressing care justice
 142 in the discussion on quality of life can improve the understanding of climate justice.

143 **2.3 Time-use studies and gender relations**

144 Human and societal reproduction are areas where gender studies and sustainability studies have a
 145 common interest. Failing to take reproductive work into account adequately is one major critique
 146 from gender studies towards economic and social analysis. Demography and population growth are
 147 central in the sustainability discourse. Focusing on production and leaving aside reproduction should
 148 not swap from economy to ecology (Littig, 2002). Ecological problems can be associated with a
 149 disturbed reproductive capability of ecological systems and with the impact of societal reproduction
 150 on these systems (Adam, 1997; Spitzner and Hofmeister, 1999). The amount of time invested in
 151 childcare differs highly among cultures and time in history. Only contributing analysis of the
 152 reproductive sphere of human activities allows grasping the whole impact of human activity in
 153 society-nature interactions.

154 Women's studies and feminist research have been focusing on "unpaid work" since the 1960s
 155 addressing the invisibility of unpaid (women's) work as well as the particularities and characteristics
 156 of this work, like the associated "female socialization and the question of how it comes about that
 157 women do so much more unpaid work than men" (Madörin, 2010). Since the 1990s, we have seen an
 158 increased focus of research on "care" and "care work". This shift from unpaid work to care and care
 159 work reflects a change in emphasis within feminist theory in general towards focusing on the

160 analytical category of gender, the socially constructed gender-specific role attributions and
161 expectations that essentially structure the lives of women and men.

162 Unpaid care work has been devalued as reproductive in the course of the development process of
163 modernity as a whole (Werlhof et al., 1988; Biesecker and Hofmeister, 2006; Rulffes, 2021).
164 Additionally, unpaid activities with emotional relationship aspects like caring are the least likely to
165 be perceived as work, especially when measured against paid work. Feminist research focuses on
166 unpaid care work also in connection with "precautionary economics" (Biesecker et al., 2000;
167 Biesecker and Hofmeister, 2006) and in recent debates on feminist post-growth ideas (Kuhl et al.,
168 2011; Bauhardt, 2013; Dengler and Lang, 2019; Knobloch, 2019). Gender budgeting approaches and
169 the need for feminist complements to the Green New Deal is planned in some countries (Cohen and
170 MacGregor, 2020). If they aim at analysing public spending in terms of gender and climate justice,
171 this opens up possibilities to save emissions in the care sector as well (Schalatek, 2012). Spatial,
172 urban and transport planning must also consider care work in order to enable emission reductions. In
173 a "city of short distances" or "15 minutes city", neighbourhoods should be planned in such a way that
174 the distances between the place of residence and kindergartens/schools, shopping and employment
175 opportunities are short and can be covered on foot or by bicycle. Public transport should be geared
176 more to the times and needs of care work. Feminist research calls for a development away from the
177 car-oriented city towards the people-oriented city (Bauhardt, 1995). Time banks, for example, show a
178 way to relate care work and paid employment and thus create more socially and climate-friendly
179 working time quotas (Schor, 2016; Bader et al., 2021).

180 2.4 Functional time-use and carbon emissions

181 Time use studies comprise all daily human activities and their organization in societies. Human time
182 is a resource necessary for production and reproduction of person, family, economy and community
183 (table 1). This systemic approach translates into functional time-use categories used widely in time-
184 use research and encompass activities from time-use surveys. Social structure and institutions,
185 gendered and unequal division of work shape individual time-use patterns as much as household size
186 and distances to be covered. Communal infrastructure and public services available make a
187 difference in time use. Changing time-use patterns are, therefore, more a question of changing
188 practices than of individual behaviour. Time use, time prosperity and especially time scarcity
189 determines our quality of life (Rosa et al., 2015; Sullivan and Gershuny, 2018). Only few studies
190 investigate how time-use patterns develop in industrial society and what this means in terms of
191 environmental pressure (Jalas, 2002; Druckman et al., 2012; Smetschka et al., 2019).

Re/production of system	Functional time-use category	Encompasses activities from time-use surveys
Person	Personal time	Personal Care & Sleep
Household	Committed time	Household & Food; Family, Care & Support
Economy	Contracted time	Employment, Study, Agricultural Production
Community	Free time	Social activities, politics, culture, leisure

192 Table 1: Functional time-use categories, adapted from (Ringhofer and Fischer-Kowalski, 2016)

193 One example is the case of Austria 2010, where we analyzed carbon footprints of everyday activities
 194 in Austria, linking data from the Austrian Time-use Survey and the Austrian Household Budget
 195 Survey with the Eora-MRIO for 2009-2010 in order to estimate the household carbon footprints of all
 196 time-use activities (Smetschka et al., 2019; Wiedenhofer et al., 2018). Results show that personal,
 197 household and caring time is relatively low-carbon intense, while leisure activities show large
 198 variation in terms of CO₂e footprint/hour. The traditional gendered division of labor shapes the time-
 199 use patterns of women and men and at the same time has implications for their carbon footprints and
 200 for the organization of care and work in everyday activities.

201 3 Discussion

202 Both, time-use research and research on socio-ecological transformation and climate change provide
 203 new perspectives on questions of sustainable development and care. A focus on time-use can help to
 204 a) cross disciplinary boundaries for gender and sustainability studies, to b) provide analysis that goes
 205 beyond economic reduction and to c) show the importance of care and climate justice for research on
 206 sustainable consumption.

207 a) **Time-use research provides a new perspective on gender differences** (Druckman et al., 2012;
 208 Smetschka et al., 2019) across disciplines. A next step should be to analyse other social inequalities
 209 like age, employment status or family size beyond but not ignoring the specific financial situation.
 210 Especially aging society faces new challenges. A higher amount of older people with ample leisure
 211 time and money available may result in a relatively high environmental impact. At the same time, a
 212 growing demand of caring for older people will change the time scarcity of persons responsible for
 213 caring. A growing part of society living as singles in urban areas will raise the carbon emissions if
 214 not met with appropriate measures, like smaller flats, better insulation, sharing of services and
 215 amenities, etc. Differences in household size are important, as carbon footprints are lower when
 216 several persons share living space and amenities.

217 Time-use research can contribute to sustainability studies with new perspectives on degrowth,
 218 equality and quality of life. Time-use patterns and changes therein can be analysed as options for low
 219 carbon and energy society. For further analysis, time-use data with relevant socio-economic data
 220 (income) are necessary. Reliability and comparability of time-use data is an important issue discussed
 221 in the time-use research community. National commitments to regular surveys, along the
 222 Harmonized European Time Use Survey (HETUS) Guidelines every five years, would be very
 223 important for further research.

224 **b) Perspective on human society and their carbon footprints beyond economical reduction** and
 225 a perspective on environmental problems including all types of human activities. Time-use studies
 226 makes caring activities visible as societal necessary work and enable discussion on everyday life and
 227 gender relations. Social inequality and everyday activities have an impact on society-nature
 228 interactions, which can be measured when linking human activities to energy or material use or
 229 carbon emissions, and therefore provide a link to research on socio-ecological transformation and the
 230 search for pathways to a climate-friendly society.

231 Functional time-use categories help to focus on different layers of action possible and pathways
 232 towards low carbon society. For a good quality of life, personal time should not be reduced in hours,
 233 but environmental impact can be lower if less material and energy are required. If more caring time is
 234 necessary in an aging society or with less national welfare available, we have to find pathways to
 235 organise these tasks with as little environmental impact as possible. Work time reduction is widely

236 discussed as having three dividends (Buhl and Acosta, 2016) of lower environmental footprints,
 237 higher life satisfaction and a more equal social distribution of work, but only if it translates to sharing
 238 work, time and money among more persons. Leisure time is mostly discussed as consumption time.
 239 Adding a time perspective helps to discern other ways of spending long hours of free time with little
 240 environmental impact which mostly relate to caring and resonance (Rosa): relaxing, meeting and
 241 caring for family and friends, engaging in community work, kissing, singing, playing music, etc.

242 **c) A perspective on care and climate justice is an important focus of sustainable consumption.**

243 Time to care can be important on many levels: caring for one's own self, for relatives and expanded
 244 household members and for societal issues needs time. Additionally, unpaid care work needs more
 245 visibility in order to be shared more equally. Reassessing unpaid reproductive caring activities and
 246 other forms of (paid) work are the basis for solving some of the most urgent ecological and social
 247 problems (Biesecker and Hofmeister, 2006; Haug, 2008; Hofmeister and Mölders, 2021; Winker,
 248 2021).

249 Acceleration (Rosa and Trejo-Mathys, 2013) and time pressure (Sullivan and Gershuny, 2018) are
 250 determinants of quality of life and of the climate impacts of everyday activities, especially in the area
 251 of unpaid care work and care (Shove et al., 2009; Schor, 2010b). Time cultures, e.g. the handling of
 252 speed and waiting times and the evaluation of the short or long life of products, are seen as important
 253 factors for sustainable resource use (Rau, 2015). They are at the same time important factors in care
 254 work and housework. Sufficient time is necessary to lead a healthy life with recreation, exercise and
 255 sport (Haas, 2018; Görg et al., 2023). Time well-being as an immaterial form of well-being
 256 contributes to more climate-friendly choices (Großer et al., 2020; Rinderspacher, 1985; Rosa et al.,
 257 2015). The climate impacts of care work surely have to be discussed further (Görg et al., 2023).

258 The quality of care work depends on interaction and thus on time. Structural constraints lead to a
 259 shortage of time or a lack of time sovereignty. Time scarcity requires consumption with increased
 260 resource and energy consumption - as far as this is financially possible. In addition, higher incomes
 261 lead to higher demands, e.g. in the household sector (kitchen equipment, higher hygiene standards,
 262 increasing wellness requirements). Climate-friendly time policy (Reisch and Bietz, 2014) and care-
 263 oriented time policy (Heitkötter et al., 2009) focus on time as a lever for policies and combine the
 264 two concerns: If people have more time disponible and care work is distributed more equitably (i.e.
 265 between genders and ages), they could act in a more climate-friendly way (Hartard et al., 2006;
 266 Schor, 2010b; Rau, 2015).

267 The COVID-19 pandemic has brought a massive increase in unpaid work required in private
 268 households - mainly due to school and kindergarten closures (Farré et al., 2020; Fodor et al, 2021).
 269 Research on the impact on the carbon footprint is still largely lacking (Gerold & Geiger, 2020; Godin
 270 & Langlois, 2021). New services such as delivery and online services, working conditions (home
 271 office) and offers of the sharing economy change the mix of unpaid/paid work, personal/external
 272 labour in the care sector. How such changes affect the consumption of resources and the climate
 273 impact of care work has yet to be incorporated into existing concepts and researched.

274 Further research analyzing differences in time use linked to caring responsibilities, income, location
 275 and availability of infrastructure is crucial to assess possible pathways towards low carbon everyday
 276 life. Time available for personal self-care, care for others, for society and nature is central for
 277 pathways towards a climate-friendly living. We find some literature lately (Godin and Langlois,
 278 2021) but further research on the links between sustainable consumption, care work and lifestyles is
 279 needed. The following research questions need to be investigated: What helps people to be able to

280 spend an adequate amount of time with care work? How can a balance between committed time and
 281 other time categories lead to a high level of well-being? And how can a balance between committed
 282 time and other time categories lead to a low level of CO2 emissions in everyday life?

283 A time perspective helps to analyse socio-ecological interactions and to redefine and expand the
 284 concept of work (Biesecker and Hofmeister, 2006; Biesecker et al., 2012). A re-evaluation of
 285 different forms of work, paid and unpaid, for production and reproduction of person, household,
 286 economy and society lead to more gender justice. "If greater leeway in the use of time could be
 287 created through time prosperity, it would be conceivable that resource-intensive practices could be
 288 substituted with time-intensive ones in many lifeworlds" (Buhl et al., 2017). Freed-up capacities can
 289 be used for more care (Hofmeister and Mölders, 2021) and to build structures for a more just and
 290 climate-friendly life (Winker, 2021) and thus represent valuable co-benefits.

291 Here we present a theoretical framework for conducting further research in the field of time, care and
 292 gender studies towards sustainable development. How we spend our time matters, and not merely to
 293 our own well-being and the quality of life of our families and fellow human beings while caring for
 294 them. Actually, it is of essential importance to the ecological and social problems of our time.

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304

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